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DEMAND FORECASTING FOR CEMENT IN INDIA 2030

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ABSTRACT

The paper estimates the demand forecasting for cement in India for 2030 based on exponential demand forecasting, linear forecasting and polynomial method. Cement being an important raw material for construction and infrastructure developments it supports in constructing a better nation. Three different methods for forecasting of cement production is done. The exponential method is suitable for high economic activity in India and polynomial (degree two) for average level of economic activity and linear forecasting for a low level of economic activity in the country.

Key word: Cement demand Projection, Forecasting , Exponential forecasting method

Introduction:

India's cement industry is the second largest industry after china in the world using latest technologies and energy efficient methods of production. With the development in infrastructure, smart cities, SEZ , residential and commercial units the demand for cement is expected to grow.

The cement production increased at a CAGR of 6.44 percent from 2007 to 2016. The availability of fly ashes from thermal power plant and advanced manufacturing technology has increased production of blended cement .The demand for cement are expected to increase with the increase in infrastructure developments in tier 2 , tier 3 cities. Andhra Pradesh is the largest manufacturer of cement in the country followed by Tamil Nadu and Rajasthan

Population and Cement Production in India

S no	Year	Population in crore	Cement Production in Million Tons
1	1994	94.22	58.33
2	1995	96.05	64.53
3	1996	97.89	69.98
4	1997	99.74	76.74
5	1998	101.6	81.67
6	1999	103.5	94.21
7	2000	105.3	93.61
8	2001	107.1	102.4
9	2002	109	111.35
10	2003	110.8	117.5
11	2004	112.6	127.57
12	2005	114.4	141.81
13	2006	116.2	155.66
14	2007	118	168.32
15	2008	119.7	181.61
16	2009	121.4	186
17	2010	123.1	206.6
18	2011	124.1	216.1
19	2012	126.3	230.5
20	2013	127.9	248.2
21	2014	129.4	255.8
22	2015	130.9	270.3
23	2016	132.4	282.7

Exponential Regression Method of Forecasting:

Population in Crore (Scenario)	Cement Production in Million Tons(Projection)
134.2	320.4868
135.8	342.5992
137.3	364.7132
138.8	388.2545
140.3	413.3155
141.8	439.994
143.3	468.3946
144.7	496.5535
146.1	526.4052
147.5	558.0515
148.8	589.1384
150.2	624.5561
151.5	659.3478
152.7	693.181

This is an exponential method of demand forecasting . Here the demand for cement production is expected to increase at an exponential increasing rate compared to the rate of increase in population. In this method the production of cement is estimated for 693.2 million tons for a population level of 152.7 crore. This method assumes that the residential , commercial and Government projects are at increasing and very favourable economic condition.

Polynomial Regression Method of Forecasting (Degree Two)

Population in Crore (Scenario)	Cement Production in Million Tons(Projection)
134.2	287.633544
135.8	300.101704
137.3	311.984044
138.8	324.053584
140.3	336.310324
141.8	348.754264
143.3	361.385404
144.7	373.343364
146.1	385.464396
147.5	397.7485
148.8	409.301184
150.2	421.899784
151.5	433.7445
152.7	444.802884

This is an polynomial method of demand forecasting of degree two . Here the demand for cement production is expected to increase at a increasing rate compared to the rate of increase in population. In this method the production of cement is estimated for 444 million tons for a population level of 152.7 crore. This method assumes that the residential , commercial and Government projects are at increasing and favourable economic condition.

Linear Regression Forecasting :

Population in Crore (Scenario)	Cement Production in Million Tons(Projection)
134.2	274.21082
135.8	283.72618
137.3	292.64683
138.8	301.56748
140.3	310.48813
141.8	319.40878
143.3	328.32943
144.7	336.65537
146.1	344.98131
147.5	353.30725
148.8	361.03848
150.2	369.36442
151.5	377.09565
152.7	384.23217

This is a simple linear method of demand forecasting . In this method the production of cement is estimated for 384.2 million tons for a population level of 152.7 crore. This method assumes that the residential , commercial and Government projects are of moderate level of economic activity.

Combined Methods

